

Newtonian Mechanics as the Driver of Special Relativity? Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that special relativity (i.e. the Lorentz transform) seems to follow from the Newtonian ideas of momentum, $p=mv$, and kinetic energy, $KE=.5m_0 v \cdot v$ or $.5 m_0 vv$ in one dimension. We argued that m_0 , rest mass, represents impedance, and that if p is physical (which it is due to impulse), then perhaps $KE=.5mvv$ represents a change in the impedance of rest mass/inertia. We then wrote a transformation from m_0 , $p=0$ to $p=m(v)v$ and $E=m(v)*constant$ and tried to argue that a Lorentz transformation emerges in such a manner.

Here, we try to clarify these ideas and obtain the factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ quantitatively by first starting with m_0 as a physical concept (inertia) and momentum, m_0*v (Newtonian) as impulse. We ask: Why does one need the concept of energy and try to argue that momentum does not provide enough information because $m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. This seems to imply that one must have $m(v)$ such that $m(v=0) = m_0$. We then argue that $d/d vv \ m(v) = .5 m_0$ from which we are able to solve for $m(v)$ explicitly without directly using any notion of transformation matrix by arguing that the information available for $v \rightarrow 0$ and $v \rightarrow c$ must force a general power law expansion (with pole powers as well) to yield a unique solution with no free parameters.

Part I Recap

In Part 1, we considered the Newtonian concepts:

$KE=.5m_0 vv$ (one dimension) and $p=mv$ ((1)) and took them to exist a priori and further argued that both are physical.

We suggested that m_0 is inertia (impedance) and $p=mv$, flux of impedance and $KE= .5 p v$, i.e. $.5 * flux of momentum$. As a result, we suggested that m_0 in a rest frame represents inertia/impedance and that if one acts on it with a force, one obtains $m(v)$ such that for $v \ll c$ one has: $m(v) = m_0*constant + .5m_0 vv$ and also $p=m(v)v = mv$ in the $v \ll c$ limit. C is an upper bound speed which must exist because force increases $m(v)$ so that it becomes increasingly difficult to accelerate a particle. Thus, in Part I, we argued for a pole with the form: $1/(1-vv/cc)$ power n where $n > 0$. Here, we wish to obtain quantitatively $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ without directly using Newtonian mechanics.

Why is the Concept of Energy Required?

We start by asking: Why isn't it sufficient to have m_0 (rest mass as inertia) and momentum m_0*v as impulse without requiring any notion of energy? Rest mass, m_0 , is known to be inertia/impedance because a force is required to start it moving. The flux of this

inertia/impedance is $m_0 \cdot v$ and may be experimentally shown to create an impulse. In fact, one may experimentally show that nonrelativistically:

$$m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2 \text{ means that the same impulse arises ((2))}$$

We argue that this is a key result, because if one only thinks in terms of impulse hits, one cannot distinguish $m_1 v_1$ from $m_2 v_2$. We argue that this is a problem because given a particle with rest mass m_1 , (which is linked to impedance), one may accelerate it to obtain v_1 such that $p = m_1 \cdot v_1$ is linked to impulse, but one should not lose information about inertia. There should exist a second physical quantity E such that E and p yield both m_1 and v_1 .

The question then becomes: How does one obtain E ?

It is known that a target may change p , e.g. it may bounce off a wall for example as well as change while moving through a potential field (e.g. Newtonian gravity). In the case of a target, the impulse hit (change in p is the same regardless of v), but the time for the change is shorter if v is larger. To see this, consider a very fast particle moving in a potential field which changes its p slightly in dx . The particle must have this change occur in $dx = v dt$ (to first order). Thus, the dp change is the same for slow and fast particles with $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ because one cannot distinguish the impulse hit for p 's being the same, but the time in which the hit occurs is different. dp changes in both dx and dt , with dx being a constant and $dx = v dt$ so dt is not. If one considers that a hit occurs in dx in a somewhat probabilistic manner, then dt is proportional to the amount of hit one receives with function $f(x)$ delivering the hit. Thus, $f(x) \cdot dt$ is the amount of hit a particle with v receives, but dp is the same for v_1 and v_2 if $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. Then, one has:

$$dp = f(x) \cdot dt \quad \text{or} \quad dp \cdot v = f(x) dx \quad \text{or} \quad \int m v dv = \int f(x) dx \quad ((3))$$

This is Newton's second law approach, but we do not write $dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ a priori.

At first one might consider $\int m v dv$ as an unnecessary piece of information, but it is: $\int p dv$ and specifically distinguishes between $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. Thus, $KE = \int p dv$ and $p = mv$ may be used to find both m and p (where $m = m_0$ is rest mass), something we argue is needed because m_0 is inertia and this impedance information should not disappear.

If one accelerates a particle, one does not simply obtain $m_0 v$, but also a physical contribution $\int m_0 v dv$. As in Part I, this seems to mean that one should have:

$$E(v) = m_0 \cdot \text{constant} + \int m_0 v dv \quad \text{to first order in } v \quad ((4))$$

Now, as argued in Part I, if inertial impedance $E(v)$ increases with v , then it becomes harder to accelerate the particle and it should reach some maximum speed c . Thus, $E(v/c)$ such that:

$$E(v=0) = m_0 \cdot D \quad \text{and} \quad dE/d(vv) \text{ (at } v=0) = \int m_0 \cdot D \quad ((5)) \quad D = \text{constant}$$

Secondly, for v close to c , one has a leading pole: $E(v \approx c) = \text{constant}/(1-vv/cc)^n$ ($n > 0$) ((6))

$E(v)$ has to diverge in order to force an upper bound speed c .

Next, consider: $E(v) = \sum_i c_i / (1-vv/cc)^{n_i} + \sum_j a_j (vv)^{j}$ ((7))

For ((5)) to hold: $E(v=0) = \sum_i c_i + a_0 = m_0 D$ ((8a)) and

dE/dv at $vv=0 = .5m_0 D = \sum_i c_i n_i + a_1$ ((8b))

In general, the a_i 's are completely independent of the c_i 's. The c_i 's cannot be 0, but the a_i 's can and ((5)) may be satisfied. One cannot have any free parameters because is seeking a unique solution based on the information given in ((5)) and ((6))

((8a)) and ((8b)) represent two equations and so there should be two unknowns, namely c_j and n_j if ((8a)) and ((8b)) are the only pieces of information available. Then ((8a)) and ((8b)) yields:

$E(v) = D m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((9)) where $D=cc$ so that one obtains the correction $.5m_0 v$ if $v \ll c$.

Then $p(v) = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((10))

As a result, we argue that one does not need to introduce a Lorentz transformation and use: $EE - ppcc = E'E' - p'p'cc$ to obtain ((9)) and ((10)). These results and the Lorentz transformation seem to follow from: ((9)) and ((10)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that one may use Newtonian mechanics (or derive its essential features) and argue that if m_0 is inertia/impedance, it does not suffice to have an inertial flux (i.e. momentum) define all possible information about interactions. $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ represents the same impulse hit, but one should not lose information about impedance and so we argue that a second physical function should exist, namely $E = m(v)D$, where D is a constant. E and p then allow one to find m_0, v . We then argue that if one accelerates a particle, its E increases such that one reaches an upper bound speed c . We argue that for $v \ll c$, one has $E = m_0 * D + .5m_0 v$, but at v close to c , one has a leading pole: $1/(1-vv/cc)^n$, $n > 0$. This is the only information that may be used to find $E(v)$ and $p(v)$. We then use: $E(v) = \sum_i c_i / (1-vv/cc)^{n_i} + \sum_j a_j (vv)^{j}$ and show that a specific solution with no free parameters only

appears for $E(v) = \frac{m_0 c^2}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}}$. Thus, we argue that one does not need to use the usual: $E^2 - p^2 c^2 = E'^2 - p'^2 c^2$ argument to find $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.